

Heat induced structural transitions of PA1 and PA2 albumins from pea

Ruifen Li^{a,*}, Gökhan Uğur Atıl^a, Antara Pal^{b,c}, Nykola C. Jones^d,
Henrik Vinther Sørensen^e, Søren Vrønning Hoffmann^d, Jan Skov Pedersen^{f,**},
Milena Corredig^{a,g,***}

^a Department of Food Science, Aarhus University, DK-8200, Aarhus, Denmark

^b Biomedical Science, Malmö University, Malmö, Sweden

^c Biofilms Research Center for Biointerfaces, Malmö, Sweden

^d ISA, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Aarhus University, Ny Munkegade 120, Aarhus C, DK-8000, Denmark

^e MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University, 22100, Sweden

^f Interdisciplinary Nanoscience Center, Department of Chemistry, Aarhus University, DK-8000 Aarhus, Denmark

^g Department of Process and Life Science Engineering, Lund University, 22100, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Pea albumins

PA1

PA2

SAXS

Structure

Secondary structure

Thermal behaviors

ABSTRACT

Pea albumins are the soluble fraction of pea proteins, recovered as a side stream of the isoelectric precipitation. The time-resolved heat-induced structural transitions of the whole fraction of pea albumin (PA) were studied by evaluating the structure of the two main fractions, PA1 and PA2. Synchrotron radiation circular dichroism (SR-CD) spectroscopy showed that the secondary structure signature for PA1 remained unchanged at temperatures up to 85 °C. In contrast, PA2 underwent a change in secondary structure between 45 and 70 °C. These thermal transitions were also confirmed by Nano Differential Scanning Calorimetry (Nano-DSC). Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) *in situ* experiments were also carried out, and high-resolution structural models of PA1 and PA2, derived from the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database, were used for data analysis. PA1 maintained a consistent local structure with a radius of gyration ~ 17 Å across all temperatures, but formed small soluble aggregates above 60 °C, as evidenced by an upturn at low q . PA2 scattering resulted from its dimeric structures and transitioned to unfolded structures after 60 °C. The unfractionated PA scattering showed good agreement with a linear combination of PA1 and PA2 scattering. This was also confirmed by the structural behavior of the purified PA1+PA2 mixture, which closely resembled that of PA2, though the PA2 component remained partially folded even after heating above 70 °C. This study brings new knowledge on the contribution of the two main components of pea albumins in the thermal behavior of this novel extract, with great potential to be used as a functional food ingredient.

1. Introduction

Pea albumins, comprising 8–20 % of the total protein content of pea protein (Chéreau et al., 2016), can be recovered as a byproduct of the isoelectric precipitation of pea globulins, which make up approximately 80 % of the protein (Kimura et al., 2008). They are composed of two main fractions, PA1 and PA2, which are nutritionally important, as they account for 50 % and 16 % of the seed's sulfur-containing amino acids, respectively (Schroeder, 1982). PA1 consists of two mature forms, respectively, PA1a (molecular weight, MW 6 kDa) and PA1b (MW 4

kDa). PA1 has been extensively studied and is reported to have bioactive functionality (Higgins et al., 1986). This protein has 130 amino acid residues, and its sequence has been published in UniProt (P62927). PA2 is a larger protein with a MW of 26 kDa, and can also be subdivided into two forms PA2a and PA2b (Karaki et al., 2016), non-covalently associated, forming homodimers of MW 53 and 48 kDa, respectively (Croy et al., 1984). The PA2 monomer sequence of 230 amino acids has been published (UniProt P08688), and shows four imperfect repeat sequences of 57 amino acids in each (Higgins et al., 1987; Varadi et al., 2024). PA2, unlike the other storage proteins localized in the cytosol rather than

* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding author.

*** Corresponding author. Department of Food Science, Aarhus University, DK-8200, Aarhus, Denmark.

E-mail addresses: ruifen@food.au.dk (R. Li), jsp@chem.au.dk (J.S. Pedersen), mc@food.au.dk (M. Corredig).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2026.112498>

Received 30 October 2025; Received in revised form 22 December 2025; Accepted 23 January 2026

Available online 29 January 2026

0268-005X/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

within protein bodies, has four calcium-binding sites (Croy et al., 1984; Higgins et al., 1987; Varadi et al., 2024).

Pea albumins have great potential as food ingredients. They are soluble over a wide range of pH and have promising surface properties, making them interesting ingredients in emulsions and foams agents (Li, Lamolinairie, et al., 2025; Mundi & Aluko, 2012; Yang, de Wit et al., 2022; Yang, Kornet, et al., 2022). However, for a better utilization of these protein isolates, it is important to understand the properties of the components in much more detail. A recent study (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025) has shown that the structure of PA1 and PA2, extracted from the albumin isolates can be described well based on high resolution structural models. Furthermore, that PA formed large aggregates when subjected to extensive heating (90 °C, 1 & 5 min), and the main two fractions, PA1 and PA2, showed different aggregates when processed individually or when present in the original extract. These results set the basis for a more detailed study of the heating stability of PA1 and PA2 fractions at various temperatures, to understand the contribution of the main protein fractions during the heat-induced denaturation of pea albumin isolates.

In the present study the thermal stability, secondary structure changes and further structural transitions in the temperature range from 25 to 85 °C for PA1 and PA2 were investigated using nano differential scanning calorimetry (Nano-DSC), synchrotron radiation circular dichroism (SR-CD) spectroscopy and synchrotron small-angle x-ray scattering (SAXS). The details of the structural changes of the proteins, based on their CD and SAXS signal at various temperatures, were then obtained by comparing them to their high resolution structural models. The study brings new knowledge towards a full utilization of this important protein fraction from pea, for a better understanding of how to employ it in new sustainable food products.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Pea protein concentrate powder (55 % protein content, w/w), produced via milling and air classification, was generously provided by Vestkorn A/S (Holstebro, Denmark). Lipids and carbohydrates were also present in the concentrate.

The other chemicals, sodium hydroxide, monosodium phosphate, disodium phosphate, sodium chloride and sodium azide, used in this study are analytical grades and obtained from Merck (Merck Life Science A/S, Søborg, Denmark).

2.2. Sample preparation

A diagram presenting an overview of sample preparation can be found in Fig. 1. The albumins isolate (PA) were extracted from the pea protein concentrate after isoelectric precipitation of the globulins as described in an earlier report (Li et al., 2024). In brief, the protein extract was centrifuged (Sigma 4-16 KS, Sigma Laborzentrifugen GmbH,

Osterode am Harz, Germany) at 10 000 × g for 30 min at 4 °C and at pH 4.5. Small molecules, including salt and sugars were reduced using dialysis (cut off MW 3.5 kDa) and followed by freeze-drying. The powder contained ~70 % (w/w) (± 0.1) of protein determined using a Pierce BCA protein assay kit (Thermo Scientific, Rockford, U.S.A.) and ~30 % (w/w) (± 0.2) of carbohydrates, measured using the Phenol-Sulfuric Acid Method (Nielsen, 2010), and the ash content measured was only approximately 0.2 ± 0.01 % (w/w).

Considering the presence of impurities and carbohydrates in the unrefined fractions, to better understand the mechanism governing the proteins thermal properties, the albumin fractions, PA1 and PA2, were further purified from the PA isolate using preparative size exclusion chromatography as previously reported (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025). In brief, the separation was performed using 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer with 150 mM NaCl and 0.2 mg/mL sodium azide (pH 7.2), using a Sephacryl S-100 resin (HiPrep 16/60, Cytiva, USA). PA1 and PA2 were collected based on their peaks as shown in Fig. 1. The fraction purity was confirmed by SDS-PAGE, as shown in our previous study (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025), where the molecular weight of PA1 was approximately 10 kDa, while that of PA2 was 25 kDa, in agreement with other previous reports (Kornet et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2000). The samples were desalted using a 3 kDa dialysis tube, freeze-dried into powder, and stored at -20 °C until further use. In addition to analyzing PA1 and PA2 in isolation, the original PA preparation as well as a mix of the purified PA1 and PA2 were measured.

2.3. Nano differential scanning calorimetry (Nano-DSC)

The protein thermal transitions and the related thermodynamic parameters were measured using a Nano-DSC (NanoAnalyze, TA Instruments, USA), which generally does not require curve deconvolution. The Protein powders were rehydrated in Milli-Q water at concentration of 10 mg/mL, w/v, and pH adjusted to pH 7 using 1 mM NaOH. Preliminary experiments were conducted with 5, 7.5 and 10 mg/mL to ensure no effect of concentration in the thermal transitions. Before the injection, all samples and water were degassed for 15 min. The measurements were conducted by heating from 25 to 110 °C, with a scanning rate of 1 °C min⁻¹, at a constant pressure of 5 atm. A Milli-Q water to Milli-Q water scan was used as a blank and subtracted from the measurements. The baseline and thermodynamic parameters calculations were performed using NanoAnalyze (TA Instruments, United States) software, and applying Gaussian fitting to the thermal transitions to obtain a peak temperature (T_d) and a corresponding enthalpy change (ΔH).

2.4. Synchrotron radiation circular dichroism (SR-CD) spectroscopy

SR-CD measurements were conducted at the CD beamline ASTRID2 synchrotron radiation source (ISA, Department of Physics & Astronomy, Aarhus University, Denmark) using a quartz cell with a nominal path length of 0.1 mm (Hellma type 121.000), accurately determined using

Fig. 1. Overview of the preparation of purified pea albumin fractions PA1 and PA2 using size exclusion chromatography (SEC).

an interference technique (Hoffmann, & van de Weert, 2016). The far-UV SR-CD spectra were recorded from 280 to 170 nm in 1 nm steps and a dwell time of 2 s per point for all the measurements. Scans were recorded in triplicate and a reference baseline subtracted.

For SR-CD measurements, all pea albumins' samples were rehydrated in MilliQ water, adjusted to pH 7 with NaOH and diluted to a concentration of ~1 mg/mL. This concentration was considered suitable within optical absorbance limits. Temperature scans were then recorded from 25 °C to 85 °C in steps of 2.5 °C, before returning to 25 °C using a nominal 0.1 mm pathlength Starna quartz cell type 31 B. CD spectra were converted into $\Delta\epsilon$ ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$), to have a normalized spectrum per residue for analysis of secondary structure elements using the CDSSTR method included in the SS CalcPy toolkit (Hoffmann et al., 2025). The online tool ChiraKit was used for analyzing spectral data of the SR-CD temperature measurements (Burastero et al., 2025), employing thermal unfolding methodology with spectra decomposition (SVD) analysis. For PA1, a two-state model ($N \rightleftharpoons U$) was applied to fit the spectra, while PA2 and PA required a three-state model ($N \rightleftharpoons I \rightleftharpoons U$), where N, I, and U represent native, intermediate, and unfolded states, respectively. Fitted coefficients and thermal transition points were derived from the spectral decomposition analysis according to their basis spectra fitting.

2.5. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)

SAXS experiments were performed at the CoSAXS synchrotron beamline at MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University (Lund, Sweden). Four protein solutions were prepared, namely PA1, PA2, a mixture of PA1:PA2 at 1:1 wt ratio, and the unfractionated PA, by diluting in MilliQ water to achieve a protein concentration of 5 mg/mL, which is within the range that minimizing $S(q)$ contributions while maintaining sufficient scattering intensity for accurate Guinier analysis. The pH was adjusted to 7.0. Each sample was then heated over a range of temperatures of 25, 45, 55, 60, 70, 75, and 80 °C for 2 min in a water bath, and immediately cooled down to room temperature in an ice-water bath. The heating time of 2 min is selected based on our previous papers that pea albumins are sensitive to temperature (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025). Each sample (90 μ L) was loaded into a 96-well plate and injected into a BioCube system (Xenocs) with a 1 mm diameter flow-through capillary. This setup ensured the use of the same capillary for all samples, background measurements, and normalization procedures. Measurements were performed at room temperature using X-rays with an energy of 12.42 keV. Data collection was carried out with the detector positioned at sample-to-detector distances of 2 m (scattering vector modulus range, q : 0.003–0.28 \AA^{-1}), utilizing an Eiger2 4 M detector from Dectris. Subsequent data processing involved normalization to beamline intensity and data binning, background subtraction, and conversion to an absolute scale using the scattering data from a pure water sample.

Our recent study (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025) demonstrated that SAXS data for PA1 and PA2 can be described based on the theoretical scattering from high-resolution models based on AlphaFold predictions using published sequences (P62927 and P08688). The initial native structures were then evaluated in relation to the different heated samples using the methods described elsewhere (Bærentsen et al., 2023), including the scattering from a hydration layer. A structure factor for unspecific aggregation of the high-resolution structures had to be included. In addition, some of the heat-treated samples, had a power-law scattering pattern at low q , suggesting the presence of protein large aggregates. For such cases, a power-law structure factor was incorporated into the analysis: $S(q) = 1 + a/q^b$ where a and b are fit parameters. Details on the structural models have been previously published (Bærentsen et al., 2023; Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025).

The unfractionated PA suspension, as well as the recombined PA1 and PA2 mixture, were evaluated as a linear combination of the PA1 and PA2 fractions, and a power-law scattering (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025). For the high-temperature unfolded PA2 structure, rigid-body refinement was performed on segmented domains of the predicted structure to get a

representative model. A model-independent analysis was also performed, where the radius of gyration (R_g) was determined from the high/intermediate q where the power-law does not contribute, employing a Guinier fit, when the SAXS scattering data are fitted by a straight line in the Guinier plot of $\ln(I(q))$ vs q^2 , according to the Guinier equation $I(q) = I(0)e^{-q^2 R_g^2/3}$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermal transitions of pea albumins using NanoDSC

The pea albumin fractions exhibited distinct thermal properties when in solution, as shown in Fig. 2. The PA1 fraction displayed one single major transition temperature with a peak denaturation (T_d) at approximately 75 °C. In contrast, the PA2 fraction showed less defined transition peaks starting at a lower temperature compared to PA1, with distinct transition peaks, with T_d values at approximately 55, 60, 71, 75, and 81 °C. These observations suggested that PA2 initiated its thermal transition at temperatures below 50 °C and was subjected to multiple structural changes as the heating temperature increased. The possibility that these transitions may be caused by different variants of PA2 may not be excluded, as this would also result in different T_d values in the sample. By comparing PA1 and PA2, it can be concluded that PA1 is more heat stable than PA2, confirming previous reports (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025).

The thermal transitions of unfractionated PA sample, containing PA1 and PA2, displayed three main peak temperatures at approximately 56, 72, and 80 °C. The thermal behavior of PA appeared to be dominated by PA2, as evidenced by the two high endothermic enthalpy peaks at approximately 56 and 80 °C, alongside a significantly smaller peak at ~72 °C, which coincides with the major denaturation temperature range of PA1. While these results may suggest a synergistic effect of PA1 in the PA mix, due to the larger transition peak at 80 °C, it is important to note that in the unfractionated PA sample, non-protein components, particularly soluble carbohydrates, may also influence the thermal properties of the proteins. In addition, PA1 and PA2 may be forming a complex aggregates leading to the occurrence of the broader transition peak with higher enthalpy at a T_d of 80 °C. It is worth noting that PA2, with its positive charge at neutral pH, has been reported to preferentially bind to polysaccharides compared to PA1, likely due to differences in their charge characteristics (Li et al., 2021). The carbohydrate residues could interact through hydrogen bonding and steric effects, changing the unfolding pathway and aggregation kinetics of albumins; however our current data does not allow for a full mechanistic understanding of this effect. Future work is needed to evaluate how the removal or re-addition of residual carbohydrates may affect the stability of these proteins.

3.2. Secondary structure changes

Fig. 3 shows the CD spectra of the two purified fractions PA1 and PA2, and the original, unfractionated PA. The estimated secondary structure elements of PA1 and PA2 are consistent with the predicted protein structure from AlphaFold, based on their known amino acid sequences (Varadi, & Magana, 2024). Both fractions exhibited a higher proportion of β -sheet, compared to α -helices. These findings are also consistent with previous reports using FTIR (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025). PA1 has been described as containing a stranded antiparallel β -sheet with a long flexible loop (Jouvensal et al., 2003), while PA2 having a non-helix globular structure (Higgins et al., 1987; Luo et al., 2021). In spite of being unfractionated, the CD spectrum of PA showed also features similar to the two protein fractions, indicating that these proteins were the most abundant and dominated the CD spectroscopy signal.

To evaluate the secondary structure changes occurring during heating, the samples were subjected to a temperature ramp *in situ*. Fig. 4 shows the SR-CD spectra measured at increasing temperatures. In general, all samples showed the typical secondary structure features

Fig. 2. Thermal transitions measured by NanoDSC for unfractionated pea albumin (PA, green), and the corresponding two isolated fractions, PA1 (black) and PA2 (blue). The table shows corresponding peak temperature (T_d) and enthalpy change (ΔH). All samples were measured at 10 mg/mL, in triplicate; results are reported as average \pm std. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. SR-CD spectra of unfractionated pea albumins (green), as well as of PA1 and PA2 fractions (black and blue, respectively), together with structural prediction by AlphaFold (top right) and their secondary structure elements (table, right). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

(Hoffmann et al., 2016), both for α -helix and β -sheet, by displaying a maximum positive peak at 185–190 nm, and two double minima negative peaks at \sim 205 nm and \sim 222 nm, even after heat treatment. The CD spectra of PA1 remained largely unchanged throughout the entire temperature ramp with only slight changes in the peaks. PA1 and PA2 showed distinct transitions. In the case of PA1, one major structural transition occurred at 70 °C (Fig. 4A–D), consistent with the NanoDSC data. Regardless, PA1 CD spectra remained mostly unchanged with heating, demonstrating that the secondary structure was intact after heating. In the case of PA2 (Fig. 4B–E), the CD spectra was constant at temperatures below \sim 45 °C, and exhibited continuous changes at higher temperatures, with an increase in magnitude of both the positive and negative peaks. This behavior was also consistent with the NanoDSC data shown in Fig. 2. PA2 showed two main onsets of structural change, at 48 and 67 °C. The increase in the CD spectrum magnitude, coupled with minor changes in absorbance (Fig. S1), surprisingly, shows that at higher temperatures the secondary structure of PA2 becomes more ordered. The changes seen when increasing the temperature for the unfractionated PA (Fig. 4C–F) instead would suggest much smaller structural changes compared to those seen for PA2. The absorbance spectra measured simultaneously during the CD spectroscopy runs, while heating (shown in Fig. S1), indicates that the protein was likely forming aggregates, becoming less soluble and therefore scattering the beam. This is in agreement with visual observations (Fig. S2) of heated

samples, where PA showed a significant increase in turbidity leading to aggregation at the highest temperature. It is important to point out that additional components (i.e. soluble carbohydrates) present in PA may contribute to some of the differences observed in thermal stability. The results for PA were in agreement with other studies on albumins, for example, the unfractionated fraction extracted from sesame seeds, which also reported that these proteins maintain most of their secondary structure after heat treatment, with only partial and reversible loss of α -helix structures (Moreno et al., 2005).

3.3. Structural dynamics at multiple length scales: small angle X ray scattering

The protein preparations were also measured using SAXS after heating at selected temperatures, namely 25, 45, 55, 60, 70, 75, and 80 °C for 2 min. The SAXS intensity as a function of temperature is shown in Fig. 5. All PA1 solutions were clear throughout the heating process, whereas both PA2 and the mixture (PA1 + PA2) showed an increased turbidity at temperatures above 60 °C (Fig. S2). While these preparations showed the presence of soluble aggregates, the unfractionated PA solution turned turbid at a higher temperature (about 70 °C) and showed a precipitate at 80 °C (Supplementary Material Fig. S2). The differences between the PA1+PA2 mix and the unfractionated PA after heating suggest that the presence of other components in PA may cause

Fig. 4. SR-CD spectra of pea albumin and its fractions PA1 and PA2, as a function of temperature (left hand panel), and the corresponding coefficients of the whole CD spectra fitting from 25 to 85 °C using the thermal folding method in ChiraKit (right hand panel). Values of transition temperatures for a single (PA1) and double (PA2 and PA) transition are shown.

partial stabilization of PA2, but also the formation of larger, insoluble aggregates at higher temperatures.

The SAXS scattering patterns for PA1 (Fig. 5A) demonstrate that this protein did not lose its local structure with heating, only showing an upturn at low q , while maintaining a characteristic shape at intermediate q . As summarized in Table 1, the R_g of ~ 17 Å (local structure) for PA1, estimated using the Guinier analysis in the intermediate q range from 0.03 to 0.1 \AA^{-1} , remained unchanged through the whole heating temperature. All samples of PA1, regardless of the heating temperature, showed good agreement with the model obtained from the AlphaFold high-resolution structure (P62927), which is shown in Fig. 6. The SAXS data (Fig. 5A) agreed with the heat stability measured by Nano-DSC, as well as the unchanged secondary structure measured by synchrotron CD. The upturn in intensity measured at low q , estimated using a power-law (Table 1) shifted from $q^{-1.4}$ to $q^{-3.6}$ as the temperature increased,

implying that, albeit still soluble, more compact aggregates that lie outside the Guinier regime, formed at the higher temperatures, above 60 °C. In other words, even in the aggregates the local structure was maintained with a R_g value of ~ 17 Å.

This structural evolution of PA2 as a function of heating temperatures is shown in Fig. 5B. Large aggregates formed at this temperature, as noted by the increase in turbidity (Fig. S2). The SAXS curves indicated an upturn in intensity at the low q range, with an increase of the power-law factor (Table 1). At low temperatures, the local structures had a R_g value of 25 Å, as determined by Guinier analysis. Using AlphaFold structure predictions (using the sequence P08688), the PA2 experimental data could be explained well with a model consisting of a dimer at ≤ 60 °C and subsequently, with an unfolded structure, as displayed in Fig. 6 and Table 1. The unfolded structure of PA2 was divided using PyMOL (Molecular Graphics System, Version 1.8) (Schrodinger, 2015)

Fig. 5. Background-subtracted SAXS intensity for pea albumins (PA) and its purified fractions PA1 and PA2, and a mix of the purified PA1 and PA2 (1:1 wt ratio), measured at a concentration of 5 mg/ml, at 25 °C and after heating to 45, 55, 60, 70, 75, and 80 °C for 2 min. Lines show their corresponding model fits.

from its initial PA2 structure from AlphaFold, as described in our recent study (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025). While SAXS data suggested extensive unfolding of PA2 structure, CD spectroscopy data would suggest that the protein undergoes local structure rearrangements, with two major temperature transitions at 48 and 67 °C (Fig. 4). These rearrangements could include, for example, the reorganization of helical structures and their exposure to the solvent during the unraveling of the tertiary structure of the protein, resulting in a change of the CD signal. The low number of supramolecular aggregates (N_{agg}) estimated by both models for dimer at low temperature, and the unfolded structure after the heat transition (70 °C) suggests the presence of small aggregates under these conditions (Table 1). The changes in its secondary structure started to affect its internal local structure (indicated by the constant high- q feature) and may have contributed to the formation of the aggregates at the higher transition temperatures (as reflected by the increased power law factor). In previous work SAXS measurements of PA2 at 90 °C for 1 or 5 min (Li, Neofytos, et al., 2025). Showed the loss of the characteristic structure at intermediate q values; however, the present data would suggest very low loss of local structure with unfolding only at temperatures >70 °C. With this high resolution analysis, it was then possible to explain the structural changes occurring to the proteins present in the unfractionated PA samples. Fig. 5D shows experimental data for a mixture of the purified PA1 + PA2 in the ratio of 1:1, which could clearly display the interactions between the two purified subunits under defined conditions and can also be compared to the heat treated samples of

unfractionated PA (Fig. 5C). In both cases, a model consisting of a linear combination of the high resolution models for PA1 and PA2 was applied to analyze the SAXS data. The results are summarized in Table 1. Both samples exhibited a similar local structure, with a radius of gyration (R_g) corresponding to that of PA2. There were some obvious differences in the SAXS patterns between the two samples, especially in the low q region. The low q feature of the PA1+PA2 sample broadened starting at 70 °C, whereas unfractionated PA exhibited minimal changes in the characteristic size at intermediate q and showed an upturn at lower q values compared to PA1 + PA2. This may be due to the more extensive aggregation and visible precipitation occurring in PA compared to PA1 + PA2 mixture.

The different theoretical SAXS models were applied to both suspensions. In the case of PA1+PA2, SAXS data could be explained well by a linear combination of the PA2 dimer and unfolded PA1 at temperatures ≤ 60 °C, with a transition to an unfolded structure for PA2 at temperatures ≥ 70 °C, as summarized in Fig. 6. The model also suggested a mass for each component of 2.5 mg/mL, unchanged throughout the temperature range. This was not the case for unfractionated PA (Fig. 5C) whereby the best fit was obtained for the model consisting of a linear combination of PA1 and the dimeric form of PA2 across the entire temperature range (Fig. 6). For unfractionated PA, the calculated mass ratio of the two proteins decreased from the originally 3.5:1.5 for PA1 and PA2 at temperatures ≤ 60 °C to 2.5: 1.0 > 60 °C, accompanied by a reduction in total concentration, in full agreement with the loss of

Table 1

Parameters derived from the analysis of SAXS experimental data for unfractionated pea albumin (PA), and its purified fractions (PA1, PA2), and a mixture of PA1 + PA2. Protein solutions (5 mg/mL) were subjected to heating at 25, 45, 55, 60, 70, 75, and 80 °C for 2 min. Values of radius of gyration (R_g) and exponent from power law at low q , are shown together with the number of monomers/oligomers (N_{agg}) and mass ratio (PA1/PA2) estimated from models, and the models applied.

	T/ °C	Model	R_g (Å) from Guinier fit	N_{agg}	Power exponent	PA1/PA2
						Mass ratio estimates
		Intermediate q range			Low q range	
PA1	25	Monomer structure	17		1.4	
	45				1.4	
	55				1.5	
	60				2.2	
	70				2.8	
	75				3.2	
	80				3.6	
PA2	25	Dimer structure	25		1.0	1.1
	45				1.0	1.2
	55				1.3	1.8
	60				1.5	2.0
	70	Unfolded structure	1.6	2.0		
	75	1.8	2.1			
	80	1.9	2.1			
PA1+PA2	25	Linear combination of PA1 and PA2 (PA2 in dimer)	24		2.0	2.5: 2.5
	45				2.2	2.5: 2.5
	55				2.5	2.5: 2.5
	60				2.4	2.5: 2.5
	70	Linear combination of PA1 and PA2 (PA2 unfolded)	2.6	2.5: 2.5		
	75	2.6	2.5: 2.5			
	80	2.6	2.5: 2.5			
PA	25	Linear combination of PA1 and PA2 (PA2 in dimer)	26		2.9	3.5: 1.5
	45				2.9	3.5: 1.5
	55				2.9	3.5: 1.5
	60				3.8	3.5: 1.5
	70				3.5	2.5: 1.0
	75				4.0	2.5: 1.0
	80				4.0	2.5: 1.0

solubility of PA at the higher temperatures (Fig. S2). A close analysis of the unrefined PA sample, suggests that PA2, did not unfold at elevated temperatures. This is likely due to the presence of impurities, such as the carbohydrates, other minor proteins components, may have limited PA2 denaturation, as also shown by the delayed thermal transition measured

by Nano-DSC. The hypothesis that both PA1 and PA2 interact with soluble carbohydrate components, contributing to the formation of the large sedimented aggregates in unfractionated PA needs to be further tested.

4. Conclusions and outlook

This study provides new insights into the heat-induced changes and thermal stability of pea albumin (PA), by characterizing its two main fractions, PA1 and PA2, using a combination of advanced structural techniques. Our findings indicate that the PA1 fraction, with a radius of gyration of 17 Å, is heat-resistant, showing a thermal transition at about 75 °C, but maintaining its secondary structure intact. PA1's upturn at low q at high temperatures indicated mild aggregation. PA2 is instead more affected by heating with a gradual structural change starting at ~45 °C. Soluble aggregates were formed and visible at temperatures >60 °C, where the protein dissociated, and the structures unfolded, to then form aggregates. By studying a 1:1 mixture of pure PA1 and PA2, and comparing it to the unrefined PA fraction, it was concluded that while in the pure mixture PA2 still showed unfolding at temperatures >70 °C, this was not the case for the unrefined system, where the dimeric structure was maintained, and larger aggregates and precipitates formed, perhaps due to the presence of other contaminants, or differences in the ratio between the proteins. Compared with other widely studied plant proteins, pea albumins exhibit distinct and unusually rich thermal behavior; however, very few studies have been conducted on other plant proteins after their purification from an isolate. A key methodological advancement in this work was the integration of high-resolution structural models from the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database to interpret SR-CD and SAXS data. This approach allowed for a more precise analysis of structural transitions, linking changes in secondary and tertiary structure to specific temperature-dependent behaviors. The combination of complementary methods, SR-CD, Nano-DSC, and SAXS provided a comprehensive, time-resolved understanding of protein unfolding and aggregation, demonstrating the power of multi-technique strategies in food science research. The work also clearly demonstrated the challenges of inferring structural information from less than pure systems, with results that may be misleading if not combined with relevant models. This study provides valuable insights into the fundamental understanding of pea albumins and their fractions, highlighting the potential of these waste fractions as functional ingredients in foods.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ruifen Li: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gökhan Uğur Atıl:** Validation, Methodology. **Antara Pal:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Nykola C. Jones:** Writing –

Fig. 6. Structure changes with changes of heating temperature derived from SAXS scattering modelling for pea albumins (PA) and its purified fractions PA1 and PA2, and a mix of PA1 and PA2 (1:1 wt ratio) at a concentration of 5 mg/mL.

review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology. **Henrik Vinther Sørensen**: Software, Methodology. **Søren Vronning Hoffmann**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Jan Skov Pedersen**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Milena Corredig**: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

SR-CD measurements were conducted with the AU-CD beamline at the ASTRID2 synchrotron radiation source (ISA, Department of Physics & Astronomy, Aarhus University, Denmark). We acknowledge the MAX IV Laboratory for beamtime on the CoSAXS beamline under proposal 20230450. Research conducted at MAX IV, a Swedish national user facility, is supported by Vetenskapsrådet (Swedish Research Council, VR) under contract 2018–07152, Vinnova (Swedish Governmental Agency for Innovation Systems) under contract 2018–04969 and Formas under contract 2019-02496, Sweden. This work was funded by Novo Nordisk Fund (NNF22OC0079708)- Post Doctoral Fellowship for research within plant science, agriculture and food biotechnology, the SupraPEA project under Plant2Food (Activity number 96804) funded by the Novo Nordisk Foundation, and the Villum Fonden (37759), through the Villum investigator award, Denmark.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2026.112498>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Bærentsen, R. L., Nielsen, S. V., Skjerning, R. B., Lyngso, J., Bisiak, F., Pedersen, J. S., Gerdes, K., Sørensen, M. A., & Brodersen, D. E. (2023). Structural basis for kinase inhibition in the tripartite *E. coli* HipBST toxin–antitoxin system. *eLife*, *12*, RP90400.
- Burastero, O., Jones, N. C., Defelipe, L. A., Zavrtnik, U., Hadzi, S., Hoffmann, S. V., & Garcia-Alai, M. M. (2025). ChiraKit, an online tool for the analysis of circular dichroism spectroscopy data. *bioRxiv*, *53* (W1). W158-168.
- Chéreau, D., Videcoq, P., Ruffieux, C., Pichon, L., Motte, J.-C., Belaid, S., Ventureira, J., & Lopez, M. (2016). Combination of existing and alternative technologies to promote oilseeds and pulses proteins in food applications. *OCL*, *23*(4), Article D406.
- Croy, R. R., Hoque, M. S., Gatehouse, J. A., & Boulter, D. (1984). The major albumin proteins from pea (*Pisum sativum* L.). Purification and some properties. *Biochemical Journal*, *218*(3), 795–803.
- Higgins, T. J., Beach, L. R., Spencer, D., Chandler, P. M., Randall, P. J., Blagrove, R. J., Kortt, A. A., & Guthrie, R. E. (1987). cDNA and protein sequence of a major pea seed albumin (PA 2: M r_s ≈ 26 000). *Plant Molecular Biology*, *8*, 37–45.
- Higgins, T., Chandler, P., Randall, P., Spencer, D., Beach, L., Blagrove, R., Kortt, A., & Inglis, A. (1986). Gene structure, protein structure, and regulation of the synthesis of a sulfur-rich protein in pea seeds. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *261*(24), 11124–11130.
- Hoffmann, S. V., Fano, M., & van de Weert, M. (2016). Circular dichroism spectroscopy for structural characterization of proteins. *Analytical Techniques in the Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 223–251.
- Hoffmann, S. V., Jones, N. C., & Rodger, A. (2025). Protein secondary structure determined from independent and integrated infra-red absorbance and circular dichroism data using the algorithm SELCON. *QRB Discovery*, 1–7.
- Jouvensal, L., Quillien, L., Ferrasson, E., Rahbé, Y., Guéguen, J., & Vovelle, F. (2003). PA1b, an insecticidal protein extracted from pea seeds (*Pisum sativum*): 1H-2-D NMR study and molecular modeling. *Biochemistry*, *42*(41), 11915–11923.
- Karaki, L., Da Silva, P., Rizk, F., Chouabe, C., Chantret, N., Eyraud, V., Gressent, F., Sivignon, C., Rahioui, I., & Kahn, D. (2016). Genome-wide analysis identifies gain and loss/change of function within the small multigenic insecticidal Albumin 1 family of *Medicago truncatula*. *BMC Plant Biology*, *16*(1), 1–19.
- Kimura, A., Fukuda, T., Zhang, M., Motoyama, S., Maruyama, N., & Utsumi, S. (2008). Comparison of physicochemical properties of 7S and 11S globulins from Pea, Fava Bean, Cowpea, and French Bean with those of soybean French Bean 7S globulin exhibits excellent properties. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *56*(21), 10273–10279.
- Kornet, R., Yang, J., Venema, P., van der Linden, E., & Sagis, L. M. C. (2022). Optimizing pea protein fractionation to yield protein fractions with a high foaming and emulsifying capacity. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 126.
- Li, R., Kirkensgaard, J. J., & Corredig, M. (2024). Structural evolution of pea-derived albumins during pH and heat treatment studied with light and X-ray scattering. *Food Research International*, Article 114380.
- Li, R., Lamolinairie, J., Chiappisi, L., & Corredig, M. (2025). A time-resolved investigation at multiple-length scales of the structure of liquid foam stabilized by albumins from pea. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, *678*, 1049–1060.
- Li, R., Neofytos, D., Kirkensgaard, J. J., Pal, A., Pedersen, J. S., & Corredig, M. (2025). In-depth exploration of the structure of pea albumin, its fractions and their heating and foaming properties. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, Article 137507.
- Li, X., Yang, S., Lu, C., Long, J., Kong, X., & Hua, Y. (2021). Complexation of pea albumins with anionic polysaccharides and purification of PA1a. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *117*, Article 106670.
- Lu, B. Y., Quillien, L., & Popineau, Y. (2000). Foaming and emulsifying properties of pea albumin fractions and partial characterisation of surface-active components. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, *80*(13), 1964–1972.
- Luo, Y., Zheng, W., Shen, Q., Zhang, L., Tang, C., Song, R., Liu, S., Li, B., & Chen, Y. (2021). Adsorption kinetics and dilatational rheological properties of recombinant Pea Albumin-2 at the oil-water interface. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *120*, Article 106866.
- Moreno, F. J., Maldonado, B. M., Wellner, N., & Mills, E. C. (2005). Thermostability and in vitro digestibility of a purified major allergen 2S albumin (Ses i 1) from white sesame seeds (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta, Proteins and Proteomics*, *1752*(2), 142–153.
- Mundi, S., & Aluko, R. E. (2012). Physicochemical and functional properties of kidney bean albumin and globulin protein fractions. *Food Research International*, *48*(1), 299–306.
- Nielsen, S. S. (2010). Phenol-sulfuric acid method for total carbohydrates. *Food analysis laboratory manual*, 47–53.
- Schrodinger, L. (2015). *The PyMOL molecular graphics system* (Vol. 1, p. 8). Version.
- Schroeder, H. E. (1982). Quantitative studies on the cotyledonary proteins in the genus *Pisum*. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, *33*(7), 623–633.
- Varadi, M., Bertoni, D., Magana, P., Paramval, U., Piduchna, I., Radhakrishnan, M., Tsenkov, M., Nair, S., Mirdita, M., & Yeo, J. (2024). AlphaFold Protein Structure Database in 2024: Providing structure coverage for over 214 million protein sequences. *Nucleic Acids Research*, *52*(D1), D368–D375.
- Yang, J., de Wit, A., Diedericks, C. F., Venema, P., van der Linden, E., & Sagis, L. M. C. (2022). Foaming and emulsifying properties of extensively and mildly extracted Bambara groundnut proteins: A comparison of legumin, vicilin and albumin protein. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *123*.